

FERTILIZER METHODS AND TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. Improvement of cotton cultivation, increase of production productivity and reduction of the cost of cotton production will depend on the development of the cotton fertilization system, its proper organization of agrotechnical requirements.

Keywords. Soil fertility, fertilizer, rangeland, nitrogen, cost savings, seed, irrigated gray soils.

Fertilizer is very important in improving soil fertility. However, chemical or local fertilizers are not equally beneficial in different soil conditions. For example, 25% of the annual amount of nitrogenous fertilizers should be applied to the surface of the seepage water before sowing the seeds, and the rest during the development period. [1]

When nitrogen is used in large quantities, the plant gets sick, it pollutes the underground water, and the fertility of the soil decreases more and more. Therefore, in the future, applying fertilizers according to the prescribed rate of the fertilizer card will not only increase the yield of cotton and even save 50% of the fertilizer costs, which are wasted. [2]

In foreign countries with developed agriculture, the land is cultivated by turning it over once every 5-7 years. Energy resource savings have already been calculated when seeding the soil with no-till cultivation.

The agrophysical properties of irrigated gray soils are greatly affected by the fact that tractor wheels that work between the rows pass the field many times. [3] Density of soil layers increases, porosity, water permeability, soil composition deteriorates.

Fertilizers are a decisive factor in the system of restoring and increasing soil fertility. Increasing the efficiency of fertilizers largely depends on the methods of fertilization and the technique of its application. The use of fertilizing equipment and

the depth of application of fertilizers are of particular importance. [4] In soil fertilization, local and mineral fertilizers are spread over the surface of the soil. During plowing, the soil overturns the plowed layer and is buried in the soil.

Local fertilizers are spread with RTO-4, GOU-6 fertilizer spreaders, and mineral fertilizers are spread with RMG-4, RUM-5 and RMS-6 fertilizer spreaders.

In order to increase the effectiveness of fertilizers applied before plowing, it is necessary to plow the land with two-layer ploughs. In order to adjust the fertilizer equipment so that the fertilizer falls at a precise rate, the lower edge of the adjustment jar and the slot of the plate through which the fertilizer passes are made larger or smaller. [5] Fertilizer flows smoothly from each turbopipe (funnel) only when the pusher is pushed around the circumference of the plate.

The fertilizer spreader is adjusted to apply fertilizer at a set rate prior to feeding the cotton. [6,7] For this purpose, the cultivator-fertilizer mounted on the tractor is put into working condition, its driving right or left edge wheel is easy to rotate, the slot for the substrate is made with the same width, and the fertilizer with the size of 5 mm is put into the fertilizer jar. [8] If the fertilizer rate of the device does not differ by 10%, the fertilizer is adjusted correctly. If the difference is more or less than this, it is necessary to re-adjust the fertilizing devices.

After the fertilizer is adjusted so that the fertilizer falls at a certain rate, they are fastened with clamps. [9] When setting the fertilizer rate in the field, sometimes opening the fertilizer slots to the maximum, putting a certain kilogram of fertilizer into all the hoppers in an equal amount, driving the tractor from the beginning to the end of the card 2-3 times, and determining how much fertilizer is used. [10]

If the fertilizer is too much, it is adjusted by changing the slot. Fertilizers are applied at the specified time and in the amount, which leads to an increase in soil fertility. [11]

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